

Impact of Facebook Addiction on the Study Habits of Social Work Students: with Special Reference to Tumkur District

Saravana K

Research Scholar, Department
of Studies and Research in
Social Work, Tumkur
University, Karnataka

Dr. Loksha M. U

Assistant Professor, Department
of Studies and Research in
Social Work, Tumkur
University, Karnataka

Dr. Shivalingappa B. P

Faculty, Department of Studies
and Research in Social Work,
Tumkur University, Karnataka

ABSTRACT

The intention of this research was to inspect the amount of social work students addiction in using Facebook, the amount of their study habits such as management of time, competency in attending test, note-taking, reading, writing, field work practice, report writing, presentation of class seminar, participation in group discussion in the class and if correlation exists between the two. Researchers used the Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale (BFAS), it contains the six important elements of addiction such as salience, mood modification, tolerance, withdrawal, conflict, and relapse and the Study Habits Questionnaire (SHQ) were used to 123 Social work students from different post-graduate colleges affiliated under Tumkur University. SPSS and Excel used to compute data, researchers adopted correlation and simple percentile statistical test to examine impact of facebook addiction. The Social work students studying in different colleges in Tumkur University have largely high degree of addiction in Facebook. On the other hand they are found to exhibit low extent of practicing study related activities. Correlation analysis revealed significant yet positive coefficient values of the six Facebook addiction elements with overall study habits. Findings can be used Social work educators by integrating it in classroom activities. At the same time this study is path way for further studies with bigger scope and inclusion of demographic variables in estimating Facebook addiction, social network or online addiction are recommended.

Keywords: Facebook, Addiction, Social Work, Study

Introduction

Facebook is a social networking site and service where users can post comments, share photographs and links to news or other curiosity content on the Web, play games, chat live, and even stream live video. Shared content can be made publicly reachable, or it can be shared only between a select group of friends or family, or with a single person (Nations, 2017). Facebook is a social networking site that has become so popular among college students that it is not too farfetched to believe that social networking of this magnitude might have some negative effects on college life. Most students joined Facebook because it was associated with university-level education. Facebook is primarily used to keep up with social characteristic of college life and it is a part of the majority students' every day routine. However, students also did not seem to agree that Facebook helped their academic life (Madge *et al.*, 2009). Regular usage of Facebook was an important cause for distraction of study work (Yazedjian, Toews, & Sevin, 2008).

Facebook User

India has overtaken the United States of America (USA) to become Facebook's largest country audience with a total 241 million active users, compared to 240 million in the USA. More than half of India's Facebook users were below the age of 25; active users in India are up 27 percentages in the past six months alone, compared to growth of 12 percentage in the USA over

the same period and the 85 percentages of Facebook users in India are students (The Hindu, 2017) .

Facebook addiction on study habits Impact on Performance

The facebook being a social networking site provides an online platform on which students create profiles., promote and share information and contents and have interactions with contacts both known and unknown. A day student should spend at least 30-35 minutes by surfing facebook. They actually surf for only three to four minutes on each visit to be updated, but they severally visit facebook a day. This will lead to results that are poor and decrease the achievements. The regular usage of Facebook among college students majorly impacts on their academic performance. There were six areas connected with Facebook addiction, usage models, inspirations for Facebook utilize, personalities of facebook users, negative consequences of Facebook utilize empirical evidence of Facebook addiction, and co-morbidity. At that time, the authors were only able to locate five studies of SNS addiction. The excessive utilize of Facebook can be linked to negative effects (Kuss & Griffiths, 2011). This study contributes in several ways to the research literature of Facebook addiction. Institutions of higher learning like to develop programs and intervention schemes that will address the negative upshots of Facebook addiction (Acegen, et al., 2017).

Rationale of the Study

The impact of gadget addiction has become more and more important in the present year. Many researchers have been complete on it and it has become a global concern and is now considered a health issue (Pies, 2009) . For occurrence, Internet addiction was suggested to be considered as a reason of mental disorder and has been included in “Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorder” (Block, 2008). There were many of studies have been conducted by various researchers to examine the impact of social network sites (SNS) on study habit of students but in focus no studies have been found to examine SNS addiction on social work students’ study habit. This paper exclusively focuses on to examine the impact of Facebook addiction on Social Work trainees’ study culture.

Material Method Used

Researchers used exploratory study design, only Facebook account holding Social Work trainees on Tumkur University were universe of this study. Resarcher used purposive sample technique. Researchers used the Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale (BFAS), it contains the six important elements of addiction such as salience, mood modification, tolerance, withdrawal, conflict, and relapse and the Study Habits Questionnaire (SHQ) were used to 123 Social work students from different post-graduate colleges affiliated under Tumkur University. SPSS and Excel used to compute data, researchers adopted correlation and simple percentile statistical test to examine impact of facebook addiction.

Results and Discussion

Level of Facebook Addiction among Social Work Trainees

Table 1: Addiction Level of Facebook among Social Work Trainees

Sl. No	Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1	Salience	2.55	Moderate
2	Mood Modification	2.45	Low
3	Tolerance	2.53	Moderate
4	Withdrawal	2.43	Low
5	Conflict	2.36	Low
6	Relapse	2.46	Low
Total		2.46	Low

The above Table shows that Addiction level of facebook among Social work trainees, the overall mean result shows the level of addiction of facebook among social work trainees was identified 2.46, it described as low. The above table additional revealed the mean scores of each measurements of Facebook addiction as perceived by Social work trainees. The means scores gained for salience with =2.55, mood modification with mean score of 2.45 interpreted as low. and Tolerance with =2.53 were interpreted as Moderate, while the mean scores of withdrawal was 2.43 interpreted as low, conflict mean score was 2.36 it considered as low, and relapse were =2.46, which also was interpreted as Low. The result involves that Social work trainees who were studying in different college in Tumkur with affiliated by Tumkur University have predominantly low extent of addiction in Facebook.

Table 2: Level of Study Habit among Social Work Trainees

Sl. No	Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1	Time Management	2.31	Moderate
2	Test-taking	2.35	Moderate
3	Note-taking	2.43	Moderate
4	Reading	2.32	Moderate
5	Writing	2.58	High
6	Field Work	2.54	High
Total		2.42	Moderate

The above table was reveals that the overall mean score 2.42 interpreted as Moderate. In the study habit indicators time management with 2.31, test taking 2.35, Note-taking 2.43 and Reading 2.32 interpreted as Moderate. Hence other two indicators such as writing 2.58 and field work practice 2.54 interpreted as High.

Conclusion

The results of this study identified future implications of Facebook addiction on Social Work trainees' studies process. The higher Facebook addictions go ahead to worse extent of study patterns. Also, the amount of causation of Facebook usage towards study habits is found to be harmful and significant, which means that high the addiction in Facebook use is might lesser study habits of Social Work trainees. This study was suggested that Social Work trainees who spent slighter time in using Facebook is associated as lesser or no affinities of being addicted of using, which then increases propensity of having a fair level of study habits

REFERENCES

1. Acegen, L., Sonsona, E., Nova, A., John Jerric, T., Maurice Dence, B., & John, V. M. (2017). *INFLUENCE OF FACEBOOK ADDICTION ON STUDY HABITS OF COLLEGE STUDENTS*. Retrieved from <http://docshare04.docshare.tips: http://docshare04.docshare.tips/files/31514/315145124.pdf>
2. Block, J. (2008). Issues for DSM-V: Internet addiction. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 165(3), 306-307.
3. Kuss, D. J., & Griffiths, M. D. (2011). Excessive online social networking – Can adolescents become addicted to Facebook? *Education and Health*, 29(68), 71. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4189307/>
4. Madge, C., Meek, J., Wellens, J., & Hooley, T. (2009). Facebook, social integration and informal learning at university: 'It is more for socializing and talking to friends about work than for actually doing work. *Learning, Media, and Technology*, 34(2), 141-155.
5. Nations, D. (2017, June 06). *What Facebook is, where it came from and what it does*. Retrieved October 29, 2017, from Lifewire: <https://www.lifewire.com/what-is-facebook-3486391>
6. Pies, R. (2009). "Should DSM-V designate 'Internet addiction' a mental disorder?". *Psychiatry (Edgmont)*, 6, 31.
7. The Hindu. (2017). *India overtakes US as Facebook's No. 1 user*. SAN FRANCISCO: The Hindu. Retrieved October 27, 2017
8. Yazedjian, A., Toews, M., & Sevin, T. (2008). It's a whole new world": a qualitative exploration of college students' definitions of and strategies for college students. *Journal of College Student Development*, 49(2), 141-154.